

Realism in Quantum Mechanics: Why the Laws of Physics Are Not Physical

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Published in December, 2024

Abstract—We examine the shortcomings of materialist philosophy and materialistic realism in the context of quantum mechanics, particularly through the lens of the Copenhagen interpretation. Our aim is to demonstrate the necessity of a non-material entity that exerts influence over the physical world. By analyzing key aspects of quantum theory, we argue that this non-material entity must be none other than the laws of physics themselves. These laws, while governing physical phenomena, cannot be reduced to physical entities or material components. Instead, they represent abstract principles with an essential role in shaping and determining the behavior of the material universe. This distinction is crucial, as it reveals the inadequacy of materialism and calls for a deeper understanding of the metaphysical status of the laws of physics within quantum mechanics.

I. INTRODUCTION

In modern physics, the intersection of philosophy and quantum mechanics has revealed profound questions about the nature of reality. Materialist philosophy, which posits that only physical matter and energy constitute reality, has dominated scientific discourse for centuries. However, quantum mechanics—particularly when viewed through the Copenhagen interpretation—challenges this assumption by introducing phenomena that cannot be easily reconciled with materialist realism. Materialist realism maintains that all reality is grounded in physical entities and interactions, existing independently of any observer or non-physical influence. Yet, the strange and non-intuitive properties of quantum mechanics suggest that this worldview may be incomplete.

This paper addresses the shortcomings of materialism, arguing for the existence of a non-material entity that exerts influence over the physical world. Through an in-depth examination of the Copenhagen interpretation and other pivotal aspects of quantum theory, we propose that the laws of physics themselves act as this non-material influence. These laws, while responsible for governing and guiding physical events, do not possess any material

qualities or components. Instead, they represent abstract principles that structure and determine the behavior of the material universe. By separating these laws from material existence, we introduce a critical distinction that highlights the limits of materialism and points toward a necessary reconsideration of the metaphysical status of physical laws in quantum mechanics.

The structure of our argument is organized to address different aspects of this philosophical inquiry. In **Section 2**, we present a logical argument for the non-physical nature of the laws of physics, examining the ways in which they resist reduction to any form of physical matter or energy. This section serves as a foundation for understanding why materialism falls short in describing the very principles it relies on. Following this, **Section 3** explores the impossibility of cyclic causation within quantum mechanics, discussing how attempts to impose a closed causal loop fail without invoking a non-material governing influence, thus underscoring the limitations of a purely materialistic framework. Finally, in **Section 4**, we provide another point of view on why the cyclic causation fails. Here, we analyze how the mathematical structure and symmetry properties of these theories require an abstract, non-material understanding to fully comprehend their implications.

This layered analysis ultimately leads us to the conclusion that materialism alone cannot account for the abstract yet foundational influence of the laws of physics. These laws are essential, non-material entities that exist not as physical objects but as governing principles, challenging us to reconsider the metaphysical assumptions underlying our understanding of the physical world. By acknowledging the limitations of materialism and embracing a broader perspective, we gain deeper insight into the profound and sometimes counterintuitive nature of quantum mechanics and the universe itself.

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II. NON-PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF LAWS OF NATURE ARGUMENT

Physical laws exhibit at least five essential properties: (1) they hold universally across all times and places; (2) they are universal or statistical generalizations; (3) they are purely descriptive, free of references to specific items in the universe; (4) they are conditional; and (5) they are contingent, meaning they are not logically necessary truths. Being believed or known is not an essential property of physical laws. The debate between Regularity Theory and its opponents centers on whether additional properties are required for a proposition to qualify as a physical law. Regularity Theory maintains that these five properties are individually necessary and collectively sufficient. In contrast, rival theories —of which I seek to refute— assert that these five properties alone are insufficient, arguing that further criteria are necessary. We distinguish between the concept of the Laws of Nature or Physical Laws and the concept of Scientific Laws.

Laws of Nature are the actual principles governing the functioning of the universe. They can be thought of as the manifestation of the inherent structure or order of the cosmos—perhaps even as the embodiment of divine ideas underlying the nature of reality. These laws align with the philosophical stance of Realism, implying that they exist independently of human cognition or perception.

For example, the law of the constancy of the speed of light holds true entirely independent of human discovery or awareness. Its truth is intrinsic to the universe and would remain valid even if humans—or any other sentient beings—had never existed to observe it. These laws are not contingent upon human understanding; they are objective features of reality itself.

In contrast, Scientific Laws are human constructs—models or representations developed through observation and experimentation. They are formulated as part of our collective endeavor to describe, predict, and manipulate the world. While scientific laws strive to approximate the truths of the universe, they are fundamentally products of human intellectual effort. Their validity depends on the degree to which they align with the actual Laws of Nature. For instance, many scientific laws are derived from statistical generalizations that closely match natural phenomena, making them invaluable for prediction and application.

The distinction between these two kinds of laws is generally clear. However, two prominent philosophical theories explore the nature of physical laws in greater depth:

1. **Regularity Theory:** This posits that laws of nature are merely descriptions of observed regularities in the universe.

2. **Necessitarianism:** This argues that laws of nature express necessary relationships that dictate the behavior of the universe.

David Hume’s approach, rooted in skepticism, laid the foundation for the Regularity Theory. Hume’s skepticism, however, was arguably moderate (rather than radical) because it was grounded in empiricism, the principle that the validity of any statement must be verified through experience. This means that if a phenomenon is repeatedly observed, we can empirically confirm the reliability of the pattern each time it is witnessed. However, Hume argued that there is no guarantee that our repeated observation of a phenomenon ensures its persistence in the future. In other words, there is no necessary connection obliging the phenomena we observe today to remain identical in the future. This idea is encapsulated in Hume’s Challenge. Thus, the essence of Regularity Theory is as follows:

“The laws of the universe are merely descriptive—they describe phenomena as observed repeatedly under similar conditions, yielding consistent results. However, there is no guarantee that these laws will remain constant.”

It is evident that the standard definition of physical laws, as previously outlined, is not fully compatible with Regularity Theory. Yet this stance raises an issue, specifically related to epistemic modality.

In logic, we have logical constants, such as falsehood, which hold fixed values across all models. It is well established that any logical contradiction is necessarily impossible. Moreover, anything that is logically impossible is also physically impossible (according to epistemic modality). This implies the existence of physical laws that are necessarily fixed.

Let $\mathcal{L}$ be the set of all logical statements, and $\mathcal{P}$ be the set of all physical laws. Logical constants are elements of $\mathcal{L}$ that hold true across all possible models. Let $\Box_L$ denote logical necessity (i.e., “it

is necessarily logically the case that”), and let $\Box_P$ denote physical necessity (i.e., ”it is necessarily physically the case that”). The argument proceeds as follows:

1) **Existence of Logical Constants:**

$$\exists \phi \in \mathcal{L}, \phi \text{ is a logical constant.}$$

Logical constants, such as the falsehood $\perp$, have fixed truth values across all models.

2) **Logical Impossibility Entails Physical Impossibility:**

$$\forall \phi \in \mathcal{L}, \neg \phi \implies \Box_P(\neg \phi).$$

This asserts that any statement that is logically impossible must also be physically impossible.

3) **Contradictions are Logically Impossible:**

$$\perp \in \mathcal{L} \wedge \Box_L(\neg \perp).$$

The contradiction $\perp$ is necessarily false in any logical model.

4) **Logical Necessity Implies Physical Necessity:**

$$\Box_L(\neg \perp) \implies \Box_P(\neg \perp).$$

If a statement is logically necessary, then it must also hold as a physical necessity.

5) **Existence of Fixed Physical Laws:**

$$\exists \psi \in \mathcal{P}, \Box_P(\psi).$$

This demonstrates that at least some physical laws are necessarily fixed.

6) **Incompatibility with Regularity Theory:** Regularity Theory posits:

$$\forall \psi \in \mathcal{P}, \neg \Box_P(\psi).$$

This directly contradicts the existence of necessarily fixed physical laws, as established in Step 5.

Thus, Regularity Theory fails to account for the existence of necessary physical laws. Consequently, an alternative framework, such as Necessitarianism, which posits the real existence of physical laws, must be considered.

M.B. Altaie argues that the question of whether determinism eliminates divine intervention is more complex than it may seem. While many people assume that divine intervention was only necessary at the moment of creation and that after that the creator becomes redundant, this view relies on an unsubstantiated assumption. The assumption that the laws of nature can operate independently without any external agency must be proven before it can be accepted. Altaie suggests that if we define the laws of nature as regular phenomena occurring without

specifying their cause or explanation, then we must confront the fact that quantum mechanics tells us these phenomena are generally indeterministic. This leads to the conclusion that some agency must be involved in controlling the probabilities that govern these phenomena. However, such an agency cannot be part of the physical world because, under the rules of indeterminism, it would also require an external agency to guide it. This reasoning supports the view that any such agency would have to exist beyond the physical world.

Furthermore, Altaie points out that when we attempt to explain natural phenomena, we are essentially devising laws of physics, which are our own interpretations of the phenomena. These laws, based on a logical structure—mathematics—appear to have a strong deductive power. Over time, we have come to believe that the laws of physics are not only descriptive of nature, but also prescriptive. However, because these laws are probabilistic in nature, Altaie argues that no self-driven system can be achieved. Thus, if one argues that a deterministic universe would render God redundant, one must account for the incompleteness suggested by Gödel’s theorem and the need for an external force to drive the equations. Considering the ideas of ’t Hooft, Altaie concludes that in a deterministic universe, the divine itself must be the force behind it all, which aligns with Einstein’s view of God as the embodiment of order in the universe.

Let $\mathcal{A}$ represent an *agency*, φ denote a *phenomenon*, and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{phy}}$ represent the *physical laws*. Additionally, let $\mathbb{M}(\mathcal{A})$ indicate that $\mathcal{A}$ is *material*, $\mathbb{I}(\mathcal{A}, \varphi)$ represent that the agency $\mathcal{A}$ is *identical* to the phenomenon φ , and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{A}, \varphi)$ denote that the agency $\mathcal{A}$ *manipulates the probabilities* of the phenomenon φ .

Premise 1: Projection Postulate (Existence of an agency for manipulating probabilities)

We begin by stating the projection postulate, which guarantees that for every phenomenon φ , there exists an agency $\mathcal{A}$ that manipulates the probabilities of φ :

$$\forall \varphi (P(\varphi) \implies \exists \mathcal{A} \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{A}, \varphi))$$

This asserts that the probability distribution associated with any phenomenon φ is influenced by an agency $\mathcal{A}$.

Premise 2: Assumption (Physical laws are material and identical to phenomena)

We now make the assumption that physical laws are material and identical to the phenomena they

govern. This is represented by:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{phy}} = \{\varphi \mid \mathbb{M}(\mathcal{A}) \wedge \mathbb{I}(\mathcal{A}, \varphi)\}$$

This assumption implies that physical laws correspond to the material phenomena that they describe, where the agency $\mathcal{A}$ is material and identical to the phenomenon φ .

Premise 3: Conclusion (Physical laws require an agency)

From the first two steps, we can conclude that the physical laws require an agency $\mathcal{A}$ to manipulate the probabilities of the phenomena they describe:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{phy}} \implies \exists \mathcal{A} \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{phy}})$$

Thus, the physical laws depend on the existence of an agency $\mathcal{A}$ that manipulates the probabilities of the phenomena.

Premise 4: Infinite Regress Argument (Material agency requires another agency)

If $\mathcal{A}$ is material, then it must require another agency $\mathcal{A}'$ to manipulate its own probabilities, which leads to an infinite regress:

$$\exists \mathcal{A} \mathbb{M}(\mathcal{A}) \implies \exists \mathcal{A}' \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{A})$$

This suggests that the material agency $\mathcal{A}$ cannot be self-sustaining without the intervention of another agency.

Premise 5: Contradiction (Infinite regress is impossible)

The existence of an infinite regress is logically impossible -at least under such conditions-. Hence, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \neg \exists \mathcal{A} (\exists \mathcal{A}' \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{A})) &\implies \\ \neg (\mathbb{M}(\mathcal{A}) \implies \exists \mathcal{A}' \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{A})) & \end{aligned}$$

Thus, assuming that $\mathcal{A}$ is material leads to a contradiction due to infinite regress.

Premise 6: Conclusion (Immaterial agency)

Therefore, to avoid the contradiction, the agency $\mathcal{A}$ must be immaterial:

$$\exists \mathcal{A} \neg \mathbb{M}(\mathcal{A})$$

Thus, the agency responsible for manipulating the probabilities of physical laws cannot be material, and must be immaterial.

Final Conclusion

We conclude that physical laws are governed by an immaterial agency, resolving the contradiction of infinite regress and supporting the immaterial nature of the governing laws.

III. THE IMPOSSIBILITY OF CYCLIC CAUSATION IN QUANTUM MECHANICS

Some argue that when faced with an infinite regress, it can be avoided by assuming the existence of cyclic causation. By causation, we do not necessarily mean causality as understood in causet theory, but rather what might cause a change in the quantum state of a particle. Specifically, we refer to a set of observables that can alter the quantum state.

If we assume that physical laws are inherently material and propose that the relationship between these physical laws and the set of observables is one of cyclic causation, does this provide a solution to the problem of the impossible infinite regress? This is the question we aim to explore.

In this section, we are going to define the concept of a Hilbert space to help analyze the mathematical structure of quantum mechanics. Understanding Hilbert spaces is crucial for exploring the properties of quantum states and their transformations. We will also introduce projection operators, which play a key role in examining the interactions and transitions between different quantum states.

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in \mathbb{C} \quad \exists \mathcal{H}, \quad \forall u, v \in \mathcal{H} \quad (u + v \in \mathcal{H}) \\ \langle u, v \rangle = \langle v, u \rangle, \quad \langle \alpha u + \omega, v \rangle = \alpha \langle u, v \rangle + \langle \omega, v \rangle \\ \langle u, u \rangle \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad \langle u, u \rangle = \|u\|^2 \\ \|u_n - u_m\| \implies \exists u \|u_n - u\| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

In Figure 1, it illustrates the concept of cyclic causation within two arbitrary Hilbert spaces. Building on this, we now introduce projection operators, which are essential for understanding how quantum states transition and interact within a Hilbert space. These operators allow us to project a state from one subspace to another, providing insight into the dynamics of quantum systems.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{let } |\psi_A\rangle &\in \mathcal{H}_A, \quad |\Phi^i\rangle \in \mathcal{H}_B \\ \mathcal{P}_B &:= \sum_i |\Phi^i\rangle\langle\Phi^i| \\ \mathcal{P}_B|\psi_A\rangle &= \sum_i |\Phi_B^i\rangle\langle\Phi_B^i|\psi_A\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1: Cyclic Causation Representation

Now, we explore the concept of Hilbert space conservation under the time derivative operator, denoted as ∂_t . We begin by considering a quantum state $|\Psi(t)\rangle$ that resides in the total Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_{\text{tot}}$, which is the tensor product of two subspaces, $\mathcal{H}_A$ and $\mathcal{H}_B$. This setup allows us to express the state as a combination of states from each subspace, $|H_A\rangle$ and $|H_B\rangle$.

The time evolution of the state $|\Psi(t)\rangle$ is described by the equation $\partial_t|\Psi(t)\rangle$, which accounts for changes in both $|H_A\rangle$ and $|H_B\rangle$. This expression highlights how the dynamics of the total system can be decomposed into contributions from each subspace. The notation $\partial_t|H_A\rangle$ indicates the time derivative of the state in $\mathcal{H}_A$, and similarly for $|H_B\rangle$.

Finally, the projection operator $\mathcal{P}$ applied to $|\Psi\rangle$ ensures that the resulting state remains within the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$, maintaining the conservation of the quantum state within the defined framework. This section underscores the importance of understanding how quantum states evolve over time within composite systems.

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(t)\rangle &\in \mathcal{H}_{\text{tot}} := \mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B, \\ \therefore |\Psi(t)\rangle &:= |H_A\rangle \otimes |H_B\rangle, \\ \partial_t|\Psi(t)\rangle &= \partial_t|H_A\rangle \otimes |H_B\rangle + |H_A\rangle \otimes \partial_t|H_B\rangle, \\ \partial_t|H_A\rangle, |H_A\rangle &\in \mathcal{H}, \quad \mathcal{P}|\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{H}. \end{aligned}$$

We delve into the relationship between the Hilbert space of physical laws, denoted as $\mathcal{H}_L$, and the phenomenon space, $\mathcal{H}_P$. These spaces represent

the theoretical framework and the observable phenomena, respectively. The projection operator $\mathcal{P}_P$ is defined as a sum over basis states $|\Phi_P^i\rangle$, which allows us to project any state from the physical laws space onto the phenomenon space.

The equation $\mathcal{P}_P|\Psi_L\rangle$ illustrates how a state from the physical laws space is expressed in terms of the phenomenon space basis. Similarly, $\mathcal{P}_L|\Psi_P\rangle$ projects a state from the phenomenon space onto the physical laws space. The equivalence $\mathcal{H}_L = \mathcal{H}_P$ holds if the time derivatives of the basis states in both spaces are equal, indicating a perfect correspondence between laws and phenomena.

However, the concept of diffeomorphism covariance, where $\partial_t|\Phi_t^i\rangle = 0$, contrasts with the observation that $\partial_t|\Phi_t^i\rangle \neq 0$. This discrepancy highlights that the spaces $\mathcal{H}_L$ and $\mathcal{H}_P$ are not identical, emphasizing the complexity and potential limitations in aligning theoretical laws with observable phenomena. To sum up,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_P &:= \sum_i |\Phi_P^i\rangle\langle\Phi_P^i|, \\ \mathcal{P}_P|\Psi_L\rangle &= \sum_i |\Phi_P^i\rangle\langle\Phi_P^i|\Psi_L\rangle, \\ \mathcal{P}_L|\Psi_P\rangle &= \sum_i |\Phi_L^i\rangle\langle\Phi_L^i|\Psi_P\rangle, \\ \therefore \mathcal{H}_L = \mathcal{H}_P &\iff \partial_t|\Phi_L^i\rangle = \partial_t|\Phi_P^i\rangle, \\ \text{Diffeomorphism covariance: } &\partial_t|\Phi_t^i\rangle = 0, \\ \text{Observation: } &\partial_t|\Phi_t^i\rangle \neq 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{H}_L \neq \mathcal{H}_P.$$

This means that physical laws cannot be regarded as identical to the set of observables, nor can they be seen as influencing each other. Consequently, the interpretation of cyclic causation fails to escape the conclusion that the non-material nature of physical laws is an inevitable result of the impossible infinite regress.

IV. SEPARATING PHYSICAL LAWS FROM PHENOMENAL REALITY

In this section, we aim to demonstrate the impossibility of equating the laws of physics with observables. Let $\Pi(x)$ represent the physical laws, which are abstract principles governing the universe. Let θ denote the phenomena within the universe, observable events or states that are described by these

laws, we can formalize the argument as follows:

- Premise 1: $\Sigma = \{\theta \mid \theta \models \Pi(x)\}$
Premise 2: $\Pi = \theta$
Premise 3: Russell's Paradox applies
Conclusion: $\Pi \neq \theta$

This contradiction implies that either definition 1 is incorrect (though I believe the definition is sound based on our discussion of determinism and regularity), and this is not an assumption by exclusion. It merely introduces the potential that $\theta = \Pi$ without any restriction to avoid begging the question. When we attempted to include this in a set, a contradiction arose, indicating that they cannot be the same thing. This logical structure underscores the inherent contradiction in assuming that physical laws are identical to observable phenomena, thereby reinforcing their non-material nature.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper has explored the intricate relationship between the laws of physics and the phenomena they govern, particularly within the framework of Realism philosophy. Through a comprehensive analysis, we have argued that the laws of physics cannot be confined to a purely physical realm. Instead, they necessitate a metaphysical or non-physical interpretation to account for their abstract and universal nature. This perspective aligns with the philosophical stance that physical laws transcend the material world, providing a foundational structure that guides observable phenomena.

Furthermore, we have critically examined and refuted the notion of cyclic causation, demonstrating its inadequacy in addressing the inherent complexities of physical laws. By highlighting the logical inconsistencies and limitations of this concept, we have reinforced the argument for a non-material understanding of these laws.

Additionally, we presented a robust argument for the separation of physical laws from phenomena, employing logical notations and philosophical reasoning. This argument underscores the distinction between the abstract principles that govern the universe and the observable events that manifest within it. By doing so, we have provided a compelling case for viewing physical laws as distinct entities that are not reducible to the

phenomena they describe.

Our paper relies solely on Realism, which posits that the world exists independently of our perceptions and that scientific theories aim to describe this objective reality. Realism asserts that entities, properties, and events exist in the world regardless of human observation. This philosophical stance supports the idea that scientific laws are not mere constructs but reflect the true nature of the universe. Realism emphasizes the importance of objective truth and the belief that scientific inquiry can progressively uncover the underlying structure of reality. By grounding our analysis in Realism, we affirm that the abstract and non-material nature of physical laws is not a mere abstraction but a reflection of their role in describing an independent reality. This perspective challenges the notion that laws are simply derived from observable phenomena, instead highlighting their foundational role in shaping our understanding of the cosmos. Through this lens, we can appreciate the depth and complexity of scientific theories and their capacity to reveal the intricacies of the natural world.

Overall, this paper contributes to the ongoing discourse on the nature of physical laws, advocating for a perspective that recognizes their metaphysical essence and challenges simplistic material interpretations. This approach not only enriches our understanding of the universe but also invites further exploration into the philosophical implications of scientific inquiry.

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